

Queen of Software: Grace Murray Hopper

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Abstract

Imagine a Computer Programmer who Still programs in bits and bytes and has never heard of the terms “bug”, “debugging”. But, without the contribution of women like “Grace Murray Hopper (who developed the first Compiler)”, our computing device for general use is a simple calculator. Hopper serviced nearly 40 years in computer technology field. This paper explains about Grace Hopper contribution in Computer technology field.

Keywords: Women, Computer Science, Technology, Compiler

Introduction

Computers are used in so many fields in our daily life. Computers have taken industries and businesses to a whole new level. From ancient to modern period, women’s condition has not remained same & it kept changing with times. Women in Computing have shaped the evolution of information technology. Day to day the world is becoming a much better place with advance in technology, women’s also empowering their computer knowledge which helps them to choose their carriers in technology. Women have played a major role in computing for centuries as well as men. For almost two centuries, women have been pioneers in the origins and development of computing. Among these pioneers was a group of six women who were always remembered for their contribution in computer technology growth. So, No longer are we waiting and wondering how the latest technology will change things; we need to shape the world to fit our needs, large and small.

Born on Curiosity

Grace Hopper was one of the pioneers in the early days of electronic computers. She was born on Dec 9, 1906 in New York City; USA. She was the eldest of three children. Her Father, Walter Murray was an insurance broker. Hopper mother had a love of mathematics; she passes her vibes to her daughter Grace Hopper. From young age grace Hooper was very curious in everything; her family also supports her curious nature. They did not have any restriction in her academic.

Grace Hopper did her schooling in New York and New Jersey schools from 1916-1923. After completing her schooling, she joined B.A at Vassar college, by getting Vassar scholarship she done her Master's degree and She Submitted her PhD thesis on 1934 in the topic of "The irreducibility of algebra equations to Yale".

Amazing Grace

In 1942 Navy introduced a female division called "Women Accepted for Volunteer Emergency Service [WAVES]"; it gives opportunity to women service for their country. After knowing this Grace Hopper left her lecture job and enlisted in the US Navy and become a part of WAVES on 1943. In her Navy service she was appointed as a programming staff for the new Mark I computer at Harvard University. She also worked for Mark II and Mark III computers under a Navy Contract.

Grace Hopper found a difficult in a mechanical relays while working with Mark II computer, then she found a moth in the wire, after removing the moth the system perform properly. That was the first bug identified in the computer machine. From now the word "Bug/Debug" is used to identify the error in the program.

After servicing 6 years in Navy, She undertake a responsibility as a Senior Mathematician of "ENIAC", which is one of the world's first electronic general purpose computer. Hopper thought the human- friendly idea, which helps the people to work with computer machine who are all not familiar to working with computer machine. For that, she created a code which acts like a translator and its run by itself. In 1959, Hopper and her team invented the world's first "Compiler (A-0 System)" which takes a human friendly code and change into a machine code.

Hopper and her team worked to create a new language to do business-oriented tasks. In 1959 the team came with a new language that supports twenty business commands. Computer scientist from government and Industry got together and named a new language known as "COBOL". It based on hopper's FLOW-MATIC. Later she was named as "Grand Mother of COBOL". She continued her service in Navy as well as she contributes in Computer Science. After her retirement from Navy, she appointed as a senior consultant in Digital Equipment Corporation. She serviced in Digital Equipment Corporation till her last breath.

Awards & Achievements

- Hopper got 8 Military Awards and she received more than 40 honorary degrees from university.
- She got "Computer Sciences man of the year" and "Society of women Engineers Achievement "awards.
- She is the first programmer for Harvard Mark I. And she is well known for her Nanosecond demonstrates.
- She received "Golden Gavel Award" by Toastmasters International and she received "National Medal of Technology" by US government. She was the first individual to receive it.
- "Grace Hopper Celebration [GHC]" is the Asia's largest gathering of women technologists.

Conclusion

A legend is someone who inspires another person, they also ready to make scarifies. This fits Grace Hopper because she scarified her time to her team in to building computer technologies. She did not do it for her fame; she built it because it was needed for people then and now. A Queen will be always a Queen".

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